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THE ROLES AND IMPORTANCE OF VOCABULARY IN LEARNING ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Annotation: *The article raises the problem of using dictionaries in the process of teaching a foreign language within the framework of language education. The author places special emphasis on active work with various dictionaries to optimize and intensify the process of mastering a foreign language.*

Keywords: *foreign language, dictionary, household level, learning bilingual dictionary, vocabulary, process, communication, methodologists*

РОЛЬ И ЗНАЧЕНИЕ СЛОВА В ИЗУЧЕНИИ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

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Аннотация: *В статье поднимается проблема использования словарей в процессе обучения иностранному языку в рамках языкового образования. Особое внимание автор уделяет активной работе с различными словарями для оптимизации и интенсификации процесса освоения иностранного языка.*

Ключевые слова: *иностраннный язык, словарь, бытовой уровень, изучение двуязычного словаря, лексика, процесс, общение, методисты.*

The problem of learning foreign languages has been and remains very relevant. More and more methodologists are inclined to believe that nowadays, in addition to their native language, a person needs to know one or two foreign languages. They believe that bilingual education through the co-study of native and foreign languages is an important part of the modernization of the goals and content of the modern educational system. To communicate at the household level, it is now quite enough to know one or two of the most common languages, for example, English, German or Spanish. Therefore, in many countries of the world, as a rule, two and sometimes more foreign languages are taught at school, which is quite enough to communicate with representatives of both European and

Asian countries. As the famous author of many works on bilingualism, Scutnabb Kangas, said, it is impossible to study bilingualism and bilingual education without understanding what language is. Language is a means of communication (and not only), without which it would be impossible to exchange experience in various fields between nationalities. He believed that language is probably the only tool through which mutual understanding and interaction between representatives of various linguistic communities becomes possible. Hence, it is quite obvious that special attention should be paid to the problem of developing students' ability to effectively participate in intercultural communication.³ And in the conditions of secondary schools, one of the most appropriate ways to solve this issue is to focus on bilingual language education, where the main principle is the mandatory use of nationally oriented educational material. In this case, we mean nationally oriented material, both of the native language and the language of a foreign speaker. Therefore, in order for the process of learning a language and mastering the basics of intercultural communication to be fruitful, it is necessary to use the entire arsenal of reference material, that is, various dictionaries. Dictionaries play an important role in modern culture, they reflect the knowledge accumulated by society over the centuries. Dictionaries are used to describe and regulate language and help improve the correctness and expressiveness of the speaker's speech. The vocabulary of any living language is constantly changing and expanding. The appearance of new words reflects the development of modern science, culture and art, and unused words are marked as obsolete. The dictionary is an integral part of the culture of the nation, since many aspects of people's lives are recorded in it. Vocabulary must be learned in a system that is related to the properties of the human brain for memorizing logically organized material, analysis, synthesis and generalization. From all of the above, it is clear that a solid assimilation of vocabulary is required, which involves the performance of vocabulary work. And a dictionary is a universal learning tool that defines a word (its meaning), the key to correct pronunciation (transcription of words, stress), replenishes the stock of synonyms and antonyms, shows a particular word in context, clearly demonstrates the ways of word formation in the studied language. Therefore, it is important to teach students to use dictionaries to learn a foreign language, in this case English. Its use educates students in the need for independent and creative search for the words they need

³ Karlinsky, A. E. Working with a dictionary in high school / A. E. Karlinsky. — Text: direct // Foreign languages at school. — 2011. — No. 4. — pp. 60-68.

for speech activity, and significantly expands information about the richness of the vocabulary of the studied (English) language. Students should know how and what vocabulary to use in the classroom and beyond. There are several basic types of dictionaries that students can use: – standard monolingual dictionaries that are designed for people for whom the language being studied is their native language. – educational monolingual dictionaries that are necessary for all foreign language learners. – bilingual dictionaries that contain words in a foreign language and provide their translation into the student's native language and vice versa.⁴ Naturally, you should start with a bilingual dictionary, since it is intended to be only the key to understanding. As the student becomes more competent in the language being studied, he must move from a bilingual dictionary to an educational monolingual dictionary. According to the modern requirements of the Federal State Educational Standard, upon completion of studying the discipline "Foreign Language", students must possess a number of competencies, namely: communicative competence, that is, be able to formulate their thoughts, both orally and in writing, be able to maintain a dialogue with an interlocutor and utter a small monologue in a foreign language. Also, for productive communication, it is necessary to know about the features of statements due to their communicative tasks and the communication situation. And in order to achieve this goal, you need to spend more time working with the dictionary. The basis of each lesson should be the work on practicing correct pronunciation, on developing the skills to clearly and expressively present one's thought in oral speech, as well as work on enriching one's vocabulary and acquiring the skills to adequately, appropriately and competently (spelling competently) use words and phrases in a coherent statement. Work on the study of vocabulary material at school is of great educational and practical importance, as it expands students' knowledge of the language, introduces them to the unit of speech — in a word, is the main source of vocabulary enrichment. Vocabulary work helps to draw students' attention to the meaning and use of words, develops their need to search and select the necessary word for accurate expression of thought, a sense of language. And, as a result, through interest in the etymology of words, students become interested in the language as a whole. Time passes, everything changes, and the language also undergoes changes over the years. Therefore, the more often we turn to dictionaries, and preferably to authentic dictionaries, the better we will master

⁴ Alqahtani, (2015). The importance of vocabulary in language learning and how to be taught

foreign language, and it will be easier for us to communicate with a foreign speaker, both at the household level and on professional issues. Teaching rational methods of using a dictionary should not be in isolation from other sections of language work. On the contrary, learning to work with a dictionary should contribute to deepening and expanding knowledge in the field of grammar, phonetics, vocabulary and spelling. Using a dictionary is a successful and time—tested work that will help everyone who is interested in learning a foreign language to get closer to bilingualism, which is a very important aspect at this stage of society's development in difficult modern realities. So, the use of various types of dictionaries in the educational process is a prerequisite for successful mastery of foreign languages. It is working with the dictionary that gives us the opportunity to make the process of mastering a foreign language more qualitative and effective.

Vocabulary proficiency is often seen as a critical aspect of learning a foreign language, as limited vocabulary in a second language hinders successful communication. Given the importance of acquiring vocabulary, lexical knowledge occupies a central place in communicative competence and in mastering a second language. The relationship between vocabulary knowledge and language practice is complementary: vocabulary knowledge allows you to use language and vice versa. The use of language leads to an increase in vocabulary. The importance of vocabulary is demonstrated daily on and off campuses. In the classroom, the most successful students have the most adequate vocabulary. The study of lexical units plays a vital role in all language skills (for example, listening, speaking, reading and writing), in addition, it is argued that the acquisition of an adequate vocabulary is necessary for the successful use of a foreign language, since without an extensive vocabulary, the language learner will not be able to use the structures and functions that we use. perhaps he has learned to communicate intelligibly. Some studies have shown that readers learning a second language rely heavily on knowledge of vocabulary, and the lack of this knowledge is the main and greatest obstacle for readers. In the production process, when language learners have a meaning or concept that they want to express, they need to have a stock of words from which they can choose to express that meaning or concept. Many researchers claim that vocabulary is one of the most important, if not the most important component in learning a foreign language. Vocabulary learning is a crucial aspect in language learning because languages are based on words. It is almost impossible to learn a language without words; even communication between people is based on words. Recent research shows that

teaching vocabulary can be problematic, as many teachers are unsure of the best practice of teaching vocabulary and sometimes do not know where to start in order to focus on learning words. Both teachers and students agree that vocabulary acquisition is a central factor in language learning. Learning vocabulary is considered one of the most discussed parts of teaching English as a foreign language.

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